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TEACHING INNOVATIONS- BASIC PREMISE OF ALL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTES

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Abstract

Higher Educational Institutions face challenges with respect to teacher quality. Teacher development improves quality of teaching-learning and leads to innovation. The paper examines the ways and means of introducing innovation in Teaching-Learning and facilitating improvement in student quality.

Tutorials, e-teaching, concept based learning. Student Projects may be some of the basic yet rewarding ways of innovation in teaching. There are various strategies and techniques to bring about innovation in teaching. This could be through role-plays, teaching case lets, topic and power point presentations and the like. Technical discussion enhances the communication skills. Innovation in Teaching-Learning immediately leads to a vast improvement in results. This also has a large bearing on the quality education imparted by the institution.

The paper combines in its content case-study approach as also real time experiences of select organisations who have tasted a fair share of success by introducing innovative Teaching-Learning Practices. Successful implementation of such innovative practices have resulted in

creating human assets who are the intellectual capital of the economy fuelling the growth of the Nation as also heralding global relevance be it progression to higher education or employment.

Optimum results, student quality, student placements, progression to higher education and scholarly research activities are the recognisable parameters which speak about the learner-centric innovative approaches of higher education institutes. The growth of such an organization depends on how well it can innovate, ideate and incubate young learners to enhance their skills.

Key Words: Teaching, learning, innovations, student, Higher education institutes Development.

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Introduction

Quality education at all levels i.e. undergraduate, post-graduate, professional courses and research programmes should be the basic objective of all Higher Education Institutes (HEIS). Transparency in candidate selection fulfilment of basic obligations of defined norms and the like in general, professional and vocational courses gain utmost importance and are very mandatory to all HEIS. However in the wake of intense competition, increased avenues, public awareness on career prospects need for enhancing global relevance and employability. HEIS are facing various challenges to initiate, sustain and enhance their quality in education and innovation in teaching-learning and research. Without supplements to the curriculum their very existence becomes questionable. Therefore innovation in the basic fields of teaching-learning does not amount to supplement the main curriculum but becomes a mandatory component for substance.

Most of the HEIS have become aware of the societal needs and have understood that by catering to the diverse needs they would get better recognition, increased student demand and enhance future prospects. Student orientation, library briefing, fundamental coaching and counseling are a part of the institute culture which are no more considered innovative practices. "Thinking out of the Box" has become success dictum of HEIS where participatory learning is encouraged.

Facilitation through specific Strategies:

A specific strategy needs to be adopted to keep oneself alive in the race for existence. Both the categories of students i.e. advanced students and slow learners needs to be taken care off by introducing specific facilitating modules. It could

be in the form of advanced level of project training, paper presentation, 'A' and 'O' levels exams, specific recognition\s to encourage the latest talents and the like. For the slow learners simpler and approachable ways of teaching would enhance their prospects of improving themselves.

Teaching-Learning Process:

Any HEIS basically gets recognised by its intelligent blood of teachers who are capable of creating intellectual capital and human assets. Who fuel the engine of economic growth and positively support the process of nation building. Prioritising core academics ensures smooth flow of academics and other curricular activities. Regular feedback on Teaching-Learning would further enhance the prospects improving the institutional image and creating learner-centric campus. Class room lectures with technological aids, seminars, workshops, student projects, internships, industrial visits and summer internships which all were considered as supplements of innovation have now become very basic and no more hold the key to innovation. A teacher has multiple roles to play as mentor, facilitator and counsellor. Every minute a new challenge surfaces giving ample opportunity to learn, unlearn and relearn. For this process an innovative syllabus and main stream curriculum is necessary. It could be the relevant value added courses, soft skill training programmes, foreign language courses, courses which emphasize on human values for the holistic enfoldment of students personality and the like. The Teaching-Learning is not a stop-gap arrangement and should be highly participatory.

Though in most of HEIS lecture method is predominant attempts should be made to introduce innovative methodologies. This will make learning more student-centric which is in

tern contributes to self-management of knowledge development and skill formation. Student-centric learning would involve case study analysis, projects and presentations, exhibition, role plays, CE talks, topic presentations, group activities industry visits and student talks.

Use of Modern Aids in Teaching:

With the word 'INNOVATION' becoming buzz-word for all developmental activities modern teaching aids facilitate a better learning environment. Audio visual learning, screening of video presentation, laptops and internet facilities, animated technical programmes, movies and documentations, OHP and LCD, video conferencing smart class rooms are a few of the basic technology enabled devices which assist the innovative teaching-learning processes.

Teacher as an additive in innovation:

Teacher-learning is more participatory in nature. Hence teacher becomes an important conduit to enhance the possibilities of innovation. The teacher act as a counsellor, mentor for the students for both academic and personal guidance. The teacher should equip the student to prepare for pre-placement training which facilitates the development of self-knowledge, educational and occupational explorations and career planning. The teacher should keep abreast with latest development in chosen field and update the students on the same. This can be easily possible teacher is actively involved in presentations, projects, research publications, attending conferences and seminars and accessing reference materials. Teaching-learning process should be carried on keeping in mind global scenario with respect to technology, business, finance and literary perspectives. The

teacher should inspire the students to utilize the learning resources to an optimum extent. The teaching community should be made aware of the factors which promote teachers development like faculty development programmes, seminars, workshops and conferences, projects both in-house and funded and qualification Upgradation. HEIS should be aware that they should encourage the teachers to become mentors and facilitators. Emphasis on ICT teaching-learning has to be handed over to the faculty members. Adequate training has to be given with specialized packages. Members of the faculty have to be well prepared in the presentation of course material using latest technology. In house training programme by domain experts should become a regular feature to train the faculty for technological Updation.

Evaluation as the parameter of innovation:

Self-appraisal and performance appraisal on teaching, research, industry interaction, and contribution to institutional development act as a good parameters to introduce innovative teaching methodologies. Feedback on teaching, innovation and research are more often quantify and qualify the teacher's aptitude. This is further supplemented by regular academic audit. The academic audit focuses on class schedules, timely and optimum syllabi coverage, departmental presentations, achievements and innovations.

Best practices in Teaching-Learning:

Suggested are a few best practices in Teaching-Learning,

General:

1. To create a student-centric campus cordial relation between students and faculty members is a must.

2. Creation of contentious student community
3. Creation of learner-concentric campus
4. Timely and optimum feedback
5. Time management skills
6. Career orientation from stake holders prospective
7. Recognition of learning talents
8. Strategy development to overcome weakness
9. Counselling on academic matters
10. Preparatory course to bridge knowledge gap

Practices specific to teaching-learning:

1. Innovation and use of modern aids
2. Participate and experiential learning for holistic development
3. Continuous, fair and transparent evaluation system
4. Transparent and merit based admission process
5. Importance to research, consultancy and knowledge enhancement
6. Timely Redressal of students grievances
7. Encouraging students to become entrepreneurs

Conclusion:

In one word innovation is NEW. It is a basic requirement of a creative thought which is original. It simplifies 'things' innovation is re-thinking, re-invent, re-consider, re-look and re-

create. 'Think bold' and "Think out of the box". Innovation is the searching a way to show the invisible to people around us. Innovation in teaching-learning is nothing but invention which refers to renewing, changing or creating more effective process or ways of doing things. It is a sure fine method of finding out effective and valuable solution to complex problem the HEIS of today are facing. At the end of the day it creates value for society with social value for friction of actions.

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